

Impossible Fibers electrospinner lab equipment guide

Model: StonyLab SB-PS-JDFSJ-4+110V

Version: 1.0

Author: Wade Ingram

Date: 2/23/2026

For detailed operation, the user guide provided by StonyLab can be found [here](#).

1. Ensure that the voltage converter is on and active, showing an input from the wall outlet of 110-120V and converting to 230-240V.
2. Turn the start up key to the on position (to the right) before then using the switch on the right side to turn on the system.
3. Once the system is booted and the screen shows the settings menu, set the voltage to zero and confirm that the voltage is not on (this redundancy is just performed for an extra layer of safety).
4. Open the hydraulic door to the electrospinner and apply foil to the drum collector.
 - a. Use tape to affix the foil to the collector so that it doesn't make noise or come undone when rotating.
5. Next load the electrospinning solution into a syringe, either by pulling the depressor while a needle tip is in the solution to suck it up, or if it's too thick, removing the plunger and pouring the solution into the syringe then re-inserting the plunger.
6. Place the plunger in the electrospinner pump, noting which pump (1 or 2) will be extruding the sample.
 - a. Ensure that you input the right syringe dimensions in the electrospinning software so that when you are extruding the protein solution, your dispensing rate will be accurate.
7. Cut silicone tubing to be the right length to reach from the syringe tip to the needle holder.
8. Next, attach polypropylene male and female luer hose barb fittings to either end of the silicone tubing, and then attach the end with the female luer lock into the syringe.
9. At the male end of the hose, attach a needle of known gauge size (if unsure, use a 20 gauge needle) and place the needle in the needle holder.
10. Using the software, move the syringe pump to directly behind the syringe plunger and push it just far enough to where a small droplet of material forms at the tip of the needle.
 - a. Wipe away the extruded droplet using a kimwipe.
11. Attach the alligator clip to the metal needle tip.
12. Measure the distance from the needle tip to the collector and write down this length (if unsure what distance start with, use the distance from needle to collector of 20cm).
13. In the software of the electrospinner, set up dispensing rate, voltage, drum rpm, etc. and note the temperature and humidity of the chamber.
 - a. If experimentation calls for it, you can program the temperature to be between a defined range with the IR heater integrated into the chamber.a

14. If working with volatile solvents, be sure that the exhaust is turned on, and open the door/window behind the electrospinner and place the ventilation tubing outside.
15. Press play on the rotating drum, syringe pump, and high voltage to begin electrospinning.
16. When spinning is finished, press stop on each function that's in use (voltage, syringe pump, rotating drum, heater, etc.).
 - a. As a secondary safety precaution before opening the electrospinning system, reduce the voltage to 0 kV as well as pressing stop on the voltage.
17. Open the electrospinner and remove the alligator clip at the syringe tip.
18. Using the software, push back the syringe pump depressor from the syringe to be able to take it off the pump.
19. Carefully remove the foil from the collection drum to preserve the sample.
 - a. Once removed, wipe down the collection drum with a kimwipe with IPA or ethanol on it
20. Close the door to the electrospinning system.
21. Dispose of any leftover solution in the syringe in the appropriate hazardous waste container before throwing away the syringe as solid hazardous waste.
22. Turn off the system using the switch on the side, along with the key in the front.